

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildirimler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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La profanation du sacré entre capitalisme culturel et redéfinition du sacré dans un cadre postcolonial, étude de cas : « The Holly Virgin Mary » de Christ OFILI 826

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Restless Female Characters in Edwidge Danticat's *Breath, Eyes, Memory*

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Abstract

Edwidge Danticat examines in *Breath, Eyes, Memory* the strongly rooted cultural traditions of Haiti and their often ruinous effect on women. The novel foregrounds how customs, particularly those talking about women purity, are used to maintain family honor but they always result in psychological and physical trauma. One of the most distressing practice is custom of testing teenagers girls to ensure their virginity, a custom that portrayed as both dehumanizing and ruinous. This inhuman act becomes an imminent symbol of how inherited customs are used as weapons to silence women voices and control their bodies.

The author, through the protagonist Sophi's hard experience, explained how such dehumanizing rituals negatively affect females' identity and hamper the possibility of right and healthy intimacy. The protagonist conflict with her body image, her sexuality, and with the relationship of her mother, Martine, unveil the long-lasting scars forced upon by those cultural expectations. The mother herself, Martine, is a victim of the same traditions, preserves the cycle of trauma, emphasizing how oppressing traditions are often transmit through generations under guise of protection and love.

Breath, Eyes, Memory, also unveils the tension between self-liberation and obedience. The protagonist, Sophi, eventually rebelled against those traditions symbolized by her rejection to continue the cycle of inherited customs with her own daughter, indicate a very important critical turning point. It underscores that it is necessary to question and resist that devastating traditions, even when those customs and traditions are deeply seeded in someone's cultural identity. Ultimately, Edwidge Danticat's narrative is a touching critique of how inherited unexamined traditions can weaken females self-determination, maintain suffering, and blur the true meaning of love and dignity.

Keywords: Women & identity, intergenerational trauma, virginity, liberation & resistance

شخصيات النساء المضطربة في رواية ادويج دانتيكات نفس, عيون, ذاكرة

الملخص

تتناول الكاتبة ايدويج دانتيكات التأثيرات السلبية للتقاليد والعادات الثقافية الموروثة في روايتها نفس, عيون, ذاكرة على النساء في المجتمع الهاييتي. تسلط الضوء في هذا العمل على كيف ان هذه الممارسات, رغم انها تقدم كوسائل لحماية الشرف وصون سمعة العائلة, للتأكد من عذرية الفتيات, وهوي عادة "الفحص" غالبا ما تلحق اذى نفسيا وجسديا عميقا للنساء. من ابرز هذه التقاليد ممارسة مؤلمة تمارس تحت غطاء الحب والرعاية, لكنها في جوهرها تمثل انتهاكا صارخا لخصوصية الجسد الانثوي وكرامته .

تجسد شخصية صوفي في الرواية الصراع الداخلي الذي تعيشه المرأة بين الطاعة للتقاليد وبين الرغبة للتحرر منها. صوفي التي خضعت لهذا الفحص القسري, تعاني من اثار نفسية مدمرة, تظهر في اضطراب علاقتها بجسدها, وفي صعوبة التواصل الحميمي وحتى في ايداء نفسها جسديا. هذه المعاناة لا تنبع فقط من الفعل ذاته بل من كونه موروثا ينقل من جيل الى اخر كما فعلت والدتها مارتين التي خضعت للفحص في طفولتها ثم فرضته على ابنتها.

الرواية تبرز التوتر بين الاجيال, حيث تتصارع مفاهيم الطاعة والتمرد, وتظهر كيف ان التقاليد غير المدروسة يمكن ان يحول الحب الى اداة للسيطرة وتكرس الخوف والعار بدلا من الكرامة والاستقرار. من خلال رحلة صوفي نحو التحرر, تدعو دانتيكات الى اعادة النظر في الموروثات الثقافية وتشجع على كسر حلقات الالم المتوارثة مؤكدة على ان الحفاظ على الكرامة لا يتحقق الا من خلال احترام حرية المرأة وحققها في تقرير مصيرها.

Introduction

To control a person, by the way he thinks and act, to try make him a copy of you is enough to make him feel like a nobody. This can be practiced through many processes; colonialism, racism, tradition, to mention some.

Colonialism is defined as control by one power over a dependent area or people, also the concept of colonialism is closely linked to that of imperialism, which is the "policy or ethos of using power and influence to control another nation or people" (Anderson, 2024).

There is a difficulty in defining the post-colonial identity, because the American colonialism imposed its language and culture and dominated many areas such as Haiti; where the story of the first part of the novel occurs (Gani, 2022). The impact is reflected on people in general and the female in particular, because they lose their own identity and struggle to obtain it and live in shock (Benn-Jhon, 2016). In addition, "The female gender is perpetually denigrated by rigorous traditions and the male construction of the female identity"(Benn-John, 2016, p.3) also "female identity is constructive entirely by and for male relations in Haitian culture, insofar as women are only given identities through marriage and the system of oppression that it entails"(Benn-John,2016).

In fact, woman was more like a doll that was moved here and there without any opinion or any words to say. Any way the whole thing that the society was completely a masculine society, where the man is the holy master, all his actions considered as a sacred and good actions, while the woman is just a slave. Being a woman is enough to be humiliated, being a black woman is a bigger problem.

Black woman "have been subject to white gazes and face condemnation because of the color of their skin from the time of slavery until present day"(Benn-John,2016, p.5).

Danticat's Novel includes revealing the shock and restless of the black women's characters due to the tyrannical colonialism in Haiti, which made them loose their identity and honor and thus lost their value as women because of Haitian customs and traditions (Cooper, 2007).

Racism also played a major role in sabotaging the psyches of black women and making them weak in a tyrannical and male-dominated society. The main theme in the novel *Breath, eyes Memory* is how the customs and traditions of a country can affect the way a person develops and being raised in Haiti.

The author: Edwidge Danticat

Edwidge Danticat, born January 19, 1969 Port-au-Prince, Haiti Haitian American author whose works focus on the lives of women and their relationships, she also addressed issues of power, injustice, and poverty" (Ojuola, 2024).

Political system caused the disintegration of Danticat's family, and this led to the flight of her parents from Haiti, but Danticat and her brother would not be able to escape with their parents, who were raised by their aunt and uncle.

Danticat's life has been affected by the political turmoil that has left her family emigrating and losing their identity.

"Eventually, Danticat and her brother were able to join their parents in Brooklyn when she was 12. They lived in a Haitian-American neighborhood where Danticat felt acutely her identity as an immigrant teenager. To cope with her disorientation, Danticat turned to literature" (Nunes et al, 2024). After immigrating to the United States at 12, she published her first short story in a youth magazine only two years later.

Her novels and short stories are fast becoming iconic representation of the immigrant experience, and what it means to be Haitian American" (Barnard College, n.d.).

Edwidge Danticat has become one of the most celebrated new novelists, a writer who evokes the wonder, terror, and heartache of her native Haiti; and the enduring strength of Haiti's women with a vibrant imagery and narrative grace that bear witness to her people's suffering and courage.

Some of her works are:

"Brother, I'm Dying"

"Krik? Krak!"

"The Farming of Bones"

"Breath, Eyes, Memory"

"The Dew Breaker"

"Create Dangerously".

Methodology

The research uses qualitative analysis of Danticat's novel *Breath, Eyes, Memory*, concentrating on thematic examination and the development of characters. Cultural references are examined in Haitian society's traditions, especially virginity testing and how those practices affect females' identity development and independence. The methodology includes a deep reading of the context that unveil the wrong practices of traditions through intergenerational characters development and comparison.

Discussion

Breath, Eyes, Memory

As one can see, the title alone is enough to make you raise one eyebrow, wondering if this is a novel about good things, and happy memories. That is what the natural mind think of. It will take everything in positive way. But on the other hand, from the view of a person who has been exposed to many difficulties in his life that made him analyze every small and big thing this title alone is enough to make him think that this novel may be psychological, may be an internal conflict.

The story is about Sophie Coco's from her younger years in Haiti to her mother's death.

A young girl leaves Haiti to come to the United States of America to meet her mother who does not really know her. The story gradually grew as Sophie grew up," who struggles to come to terms with the traumatic past of being 'tested' by her mother," Martine and she was also auditioned by her mother, Mrs. Granme lfe (Cai, 2025).

Martin lost her virginity when she was a young girl, which led to the birth of Sophie, which made her live in a nightmare and shock and eventually committed suicide.

Sophie recovered from her past with the help of her grandmother and raised Her daughter without being affected by Haitian customs and traditions.

"Over the course of the novel, Sophie must come to terms with her family, her family's past, her childhood, and her own identity"(Kadiri, 2024).

Restless Female Characters

Granme lfe

I'm in my bed after I locked the outsider door ...am I? No I'm not.

I got up again to make sure the outside door was locked ,oh it's locked .

I go back to my bed and the same idea comes to me again, am I really closed the door, oh wait I forgot to turn off the oven, no I turn it off a few minutes ago, no I didn't!!) Danticat, 1998,p.53)

These constant senseless doubts and worries are what we call a complex. In the novel, all women who we will talk about, have this psychological complex. Firstly, we will go deeper into the character of the grandmother.

Granmè Ifé: She is a" wise woman and storyteller, as the total matriarch of the Caco family. Ifé is a strong, loving figure, she's an old woman full of stories"(Danticat, 1998, p.35).

Well, it is normal to be strong as you get older ,to watch your actions and words before doing anything, but that doesn't mean that old person is a perfect person without any flaws.

The grandmother here planted doubt in her daughters hearts, although her intention was pure. She just wanted to protect her daughters virginities.

She "Used to test their virginities by physical violating them when they were girls, causing them both extreme physical and emotional pain. This pain that has trickled down to her granddaughter through in hearted generational trauma and the repetition of ritual (Otis, 2025).

Well, our grandmother had her share of suffering just because she's a woman firstly and secondly, she was a woman with black skin. It is certain that she was previously subjected to physical and psychological abuse, which made her always afraid that her daughters would go through the same suffering as her. But her intense fear was badly reflected, which led to an inherited psychological complex between the family.

The grandmother was fond of death that she was planning her future funeral. In fact, this may be a second knot or the other grandmother's fear that she won't have a good funeral after her death. She might think that she will be thrown on the road here and there because of what she has been through before, or because of her constant thinking that she was just a doll, not human in the eyes of society.

Martin

Martin is the protagonist's mother, and Granmè Ifé's daughter. She was raped at the age of 16 by a masked Macoute in a cane field on her way home from school. The rape left Martin with a child, Sophie, and a lifetime of vivid nightmares.

Being a strong mother, trying to overcome all difficulties, working tirelessly for a child who suddenly appeared in front of her after she was raped by someone you even don't know him is very difficult. A young beautiful innocent girl of the age of flowers, loses all that innocence in one minute. It's a very big shock. The child in her arms is a proof that it's no longer the same as before. First of all, this child alone is the cause of all pain. Whenever she looks at her, the bitter memories of that day will attack you and try to devour you, even though she is just a little innocent child who knows nothing.

She would think that it would be better if she keeps the child out of your sight, but in this case your body will do the job of drowning you in despair and pain instead of your child, and she already has the physical pain because of her mother's violent in attempts to check her virginity.

Martin suffers from nightmares that she has every day and night because of what happened to her when she was young. So you don't find her sitting at home a lot, and trying to occupy herself to get away from her miserable past. But because it takes great power to overcome these kinds of difficulties. Martin fails to get rid of her past because she is weak and allows the past to manipulate her present, and affects her and her innocent daughter's future. She made her daughter, Sophie, run away from her because she attempts to imitate Ifé in testing Sophie virginity and transferring the physical and psychological pain to her daughter who suffers because of that. She ends her life by committing suicide, leaving behind her the little confused daughter and the husband who couldn't understand her.

She killed herself because she couldn't bear the child inside her, as it wasn't only about the nightmares, but the matter took another turn when she starts hearing the child talking to her about bad things, and this is impossible, but she completely lost her mind when she became pregnant with this child from her husband, which made her remember again all that she suffered before and the memories of her rape came back to her. She is too weak to bear all of that, plus maybe it didn't just that what made her committed suicide, but having a black skin is enough to be a big problem. Which made her pass through many other difficulties like racism, such as degrading and trying to reduce her, and that led to living an unstable life with that pain.

Sophie Caco

The last character we will talk about is the protagonist of the novel, Sophia. Sophie Caco grows from a girl of 12 to a mother in her early 20s over the course of the novel. Born in the Haitian village, and raised there for the first 12 years of her life by her mother's sister, Tante Atie.

Sophie's life is turned upside down when her mother, Martine, who has been living in New York since Sophie's infancy, calls her to America" (Danticat, 1998, p.107).

she was afraid and reluctant to leave the only home she's ever known, "But bravely journeys to Brooklyn, where she finds herself friendless and bullied at school, (Danticat, 1998, p.109) as we mentioned before just being a woman with black skin is a problem.

She tasked with keeping her mother afloat in the midst of Martin's lingering psychological trauma and violent night terrors. As Sophie grows older, she learns more about her mother and comes to understand how violence has shaped her life, and the lives of the Caco women for generations".¹⁰

She finds out that she is the product of a violent rape. Knowing that is a shock, "and hears her mother's stories about virginity testing meant to determine purity and virginity to which her grandmother subjected both Martin and Tante Atie throughout their childhoods is another level of shock" (Mehni, n.d.).

Ones Martin suspected that her daughter had romantic feelings for her neighbor, she became tense, so she tried to check Sophie's chastity, which made Sophie mutilates herself with a pestle from the kitchen to escape from her mother's care (Danticat, 1998, p.122).

Although she ran away and married Joseph and had a child, she wasn't stable and wasn't able to enjoy sex. She only saw that she was forced to do it for her husband.

The way she destroyed her virginity affected her so much ,and when she couldn't take it any more, she went back to Haiti with her daughter to understand everything to know the reasons that made her family obsession with virginity. If she didn't, she couldn't get rid of this psychological complex, and her daughter would also inherit it.

If you want to get rid of a problem, you must face it and delve into it, not run from it, and that what Sophie did.

Conclusion

The novel *Breath, Eyes, Memory* is one of the novels that has a great impact on the reader, and the difficulties faced by those women in that era who were deprived of their freedom, and became slaves of customs and traditions that distorted their future. When we read the novel," We often wonder how people in some cultures to be very backward" Especially, these black women who didn't face what they were exposed to and don't have the ability to face this kind of violence. The research examined the destructive practices of unexamined customs and traditions when the author highlighted the how those practices could destroy the female's life and identity and how the protagonist could overcome the trauma by searching and knowing the truth about her mother sociocultural practices which led to her suicide.

In the end, as a personal opinion, the sentence that describes everything is:

at the time, having black skin itself is a problem. A problem in the childhood led to the problems of many mature people. The story shows us the effect of the psychological complex that follows a shock that affected people in their childhood or at some point in life and not exceeding this complex will lead to a lot of worse psychological states such as nightmares, fear of repetition of past ,depression, inner conflict and after all commit a suicide, by feeling that the only way to get rid of all this pain is death.

Recommendations

- Urge critical dialogues about harmful, backward traditions within communities.
- Empower women by promoting education to participate in reshaping some cultural narratives.
- Nurture intergenerational healing by encouraging cultural reform and open communications.

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليين أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

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